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DETERMINING THE LEVEL OF DIGITAL LITERACY OF LISTENERS

Jumanazarov Sirojiddin Salaydinovich

*Tashkent Regional Center of retraining and in-service of
the personnel of public education, PhD, Tashkent, UZBEKISTAN*

Аннотация: Ушбу мақолада малака ошириш жараёнида тингловчиларнинг рақамли саводхонлик даражасини аниқлаш масаласи қаралган

Таянч сўзлар: рақамлаштириш, рақамли технологиялар, ахборот-коммуникация технологиялари

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается вопрос определения уровня цифровой грамотности слушателей в процессе повышения квалификации.

Ключевые слова: цифровизация, цифровые технологии, информационные и коммуникационные технологии

Annotation: This article discusses the issue of determining the level of digital literacy of listeners in the process of professional development

Key words: digitalization, digital technologies, information and communication technologies

The active use of digital technologies in all spheres of human life is accelerating the process of radical changes not only in the economy but also in the education system. In Uzbekistan, as in other parts of the world, modern digital technologies are widely used not only in the education system, but also in various spheres of human activity. The effective use of information and communication technologies in the system of professional development is seen not as a solution to the existing problems in this system, but as a means for students to learn in a rich and interactive way.

In the system of professional development of public educators, the prestige of a teacher and the effectiveness of his activities depends not only on the level of knowledge of the course content and his pedagogical ability, but also on the level of effective application of modern digital technologies in the teaching process. Ensuring the strong integration of modern information and communication technologies and educational technologies, as well as the widespread introduction of digital technologies in education, requires teachers to constantly improve their professional skills. It plays a particularly important role in ensuring efficiency in the education system.

The digital literacy of a teacher can be determined on the basis of the skills of creating, searching, transmitting, storing, processing information, taking into

account the security criteria that can be used in the implementation of various information processes in their professional activities. To assess teachers' digital literacy, it is necessary to analyze the components of digital literacy. The study suggested the following components that define digital literacy:

- information literacy;
- computer literacy;
- communicativeness;
- media literacy;
- innovative approach.

Each of these components or indicators is evaluated according to the following aspects: knowledge (cognitive aspect), skills (technical aspect), attitude (ethical aspect). Knowledge describes a person's theoretical ideas about the importance of information in modern society, the possibilities and limitations of infocommunication technologies, the hardware and software of computers and the principles of operation of computers, and more. Skills determine a person's ability to work successfully with information in practice using new technologies. The settings reflect a person's attitude towards ethical standards when working with information and communication technologies and how well he or she follows these rules. Thus, each component of digital literacy is evaluated in terms of the aspects listed.

In a teacher's electronic or digital portfolio, you can include general information about the teacher, official documents, work experience, achievements in competitions, opportunities to use technology in their professional activities, and more.

Portfolios can be different because they are created for different purposes (finding a job, demonstrating achievements over a period of time, evaluating the achievements of the portfolio owner, etc.). There are also hybrid portfolios that solve multiple tasks at the same time and contain versatile information. Based on the analysis of the data in the digital portfolio, it is possible to draw conclusions about the teacher's knowledge and skills in the digital field. Using a systematic approach in the analysis of a digital portfolio, elements of subjectivity can be avoided in its evaluation.

We have listed above two common approaches to assessing teachers' digital literacy levels:

- assess the five components of a teacher's digital literacy in terms of cognition, technique, and ethics;
- analyze the teacher's digital portfolio.

Based on the above, it is important to assess the level of knowledge of teachers of digital technologies for the introduction and effective use of digital technologies in the system of retraining and advanced training of public educators.

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